

Short-form videos significantly degrade long-term memory performance across a diverse age: Implications of memory performance in adolescents and adults

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Abstract

Short-form videos have become highly popular in the last few years, and are engaging forms of content that many users now spend increasing amounts of time on. Due to the novelty of these platforms, there has not yet been much investigation on the impact short-form videos have on brain function. In this study, we conducted an experiment of within-subjects design, investigating the role of short-form videos in memory interference. It was found that there indeed was a significant degradation in memory performance of participants after watching short-form videos. This research provides a preliminary understanding and investigation into the effect of short-form videos on cognitive function.

1. Introduction

Social media has exploded to become one of the largest forms of entertainment and communication in our digital world today. As of 2024, teenagers spend, on average, nearly 5 hours on social media per day, with TikTok cited as one of the most popular platforms (DeAngelis, 2024; Yurieff, 2018). By 2024, TikTok has amassed nearly 5.7 billion downloads globally, becoming an ubiquitous app for entertainment (Thomala, 2024; Dixon, 2024).

However, the harms and benefits of these media, which have been notably addictive, have not been thoroughly investigated yet (Alter, 2017; Zhang et al., 2019). With the amount of time teenagers spend behind screens, it is significant to society and basic research for scholars to explore the risks of social media.

TikTok, among other short-form content on platforms such as Instagram Reels, YouTube Shorts, and WeChat Channels, uses algorithms that quickly output large amounts of information. While it is known that short-form videos have shortened and degraded attention span, the other effects are not yet known (Chiossi et al., 2023). In the past, poor memory has been associated with poor attention span (Madore et al., 2020), raising the concern of short-form videos' consequences on human memory. Furthermore, with the broad agreement that attention and memory are closely related, scholars raise the question about how long-term memory is affected by short-form videos.

Now, given this relation between attention and memory, we will first review related literature and concepts to produce a more comprehensive understanding for the reader of attention span, memory, and short-form videos.

By definition of all theoretical perspectives, long-term memory is widely agreed to be a vast repository of information and a record of past events (Cowan, 1998). It would also be difficult to argue that most individuals possess a rich, although it may be imperfect or incomplete, collection of long-term memories. While past research has shown that short-form videos have a negative impact on short-term and prospective memory, scholars have not yet studied the effect of short-form videos on long-term memory (Chiossi et al., 2023; Zheng, 2021).

So far, important concepts and explanations have been introduced to the reader for better understanding of memory and short-form video study. Now, we will review related literature about the relations between long-term memory, attention span, and short-form videos.

Considering that our brains are neuroplastic and adapt to environmental factors, previous studies have explored the effects of the digital age on cognition and wellbeing (Firth et al., 2019). Environmental and biological factors may cause changes to the structure and function of the human brain both harmful and (Levy, 1994). Alaparthy recently suggested that high use of social media has been correlated with higher distractibility and poor attentional control, magnifying the concern for the role short-form videos play in this situation (Alaparthy, 2024). Recent studies have also found that exposure to short-form videos have resulted in poor sustained attention (Lin et al., 2024). Lastly, long-term memory has also been confirmed to be closely related to attention (Oberauer, 2019). Without sufficient attention, only implicit memory is retained, which manifests in implicit memory tests and procedural memory (Cowan, 2008). It is therefore important to investigate the relationship between attention span and long-term memory in the context of short-form videos on social media.

In this study, the effect of short-form videos on long-term memory is investigated using a within-subjects design where N=20 subjects attended two 15 to 20 minute sessions with different stimuli and were tested with a long-term memory task. Sessions were 24 hours apart. During the first session, subjects engaged with a short-form video platform such as TikTok, and were tested on their long-term memory performance using word-list recall. For the second session, the same subjects were then asked to close their eyes and relax. Then, they were tested with a word-list recall task. This paper provides a quantified measure of the impact of short-form videos on

long-term memory, which is important for society to know as a detrimental effect on long-term memory can significantly alter the day-to-day experience of users.

2. Method

We conducted a study using 20 people from many backgrounds of all ages and multiple countries. Participants used either TikTok, Instagram Reels, YouTube Shorts, or WeChat Channel as their medium of short-form videos. All three platforms use similar algorithms to recommend short videos of each subjects' interest, with videos each being a few seconds to a few minutes long.

2.1 Participants

A total number of $N = 20$ participants were recruited within two days. Nine were female and 11 were male. The range of ages was 36, with the youngest participant being 13 and the oldest participant being 49 ($M = 23.95$, $SD = 11.09$). All were either friends, family, or recruited through social media, and were paid \$5 via PayPal or cash at the end of the experiment. Participants came from the United States, China, Philippines, Kenya, India, and Pakistan. Participants also used their short-video platform of choice, including TikTok, Instagram Reels, WeChat Channels, and YouTube Shorts.

2.2 Tasks

Participants were instructed to take part in the experiment by attending two sessions each, and Their changes in memory were judged by their results in a Word List Recall task. Each session was held over Zoom and was 15-20 minutes long. All participants' sessions were

between 5 PM and 11 PM in their time zone, so their memorizing capabilities could be as similar to each other as possible.

Each subject had two measurements: V, the amount of words they could remember after watching 15 minutes of short-form videos, and R, the amount of words remembered after closing their eyes and relaxing for 15 minutes.

In the first session, participants listened to the announcer read a list of 20 high-imagery, high-frequency words which were randomized for each participant, some of which were used from the University of Pittsburgh's word list memory task documentation (Dementia Epidemiology Program, n.d.). Participants could not record or write down any of the 20 words. The announcer informed participants that each word would only be read once, at a speed of one word every two seconds, drawing participants' attention and allowing them to listen carefully. Additionally, participants had their phones ready to start watching the short-form videos immediately after they were told to start. Then, the participants were instructed to watch short-form videos for 15 minutes straight with minimal distraction and in an ambient setting. After 15 minutes, they were told to list out the words they could remember out of the 20 words read aloud (V).

In the second 15 to 20 minute session, participants were given instructions to return to the same place they attended the first session. Participants could not record or note down any of the 20 words. This allowed participants to have the most similar conditions as possible in comparison to the first session, eliminating any confounding variable. Once again, the announcer read a list of 20 high-imagery, high-frequency words that were different from the first list to the participants. The participants were then instructed to immediately close their eyes and relax with

minimal distraction for 15 minutes straight. After the relaxation period, they were then instructed to list out all the words they could remember from the second list (R).

The experiment was designed as a paired t-test, which conveniently allowed us to disregard participant backgrounds in the context of generalizing to certain populations.

Figure 1

Flowchart of Word List Recall Task Procedure for Short-Form Video and Relaxation Conditions.

Note. After every session, participants were asked to recollect words.

2.3 Measures

We measured a participant’s difference in memory ability through D, the difference score. D represents the variation in memory performance between two different conditions for the same

individual, and was calculated through subtracting R by V. We then individually took the mean for R and V, comparing the distribution between the two. Lastly, we conducted a one-tailed t-test to find if the differences between R and V were significant.

2.4 Analysis

We conducted a one-tailed t-test comparing the means of the short-form video treatment and no treatment, our control group. With the brain's need for time to process information, encode it into memory, and become consolidated in order to be retained as long term memory, this long process is sensitive and therefore any change in this process interferes with memory and disrupts it long-term (Kane & Engle, 2000). Therefore, we conducted a one-tailed t-test, hypothesizing that there would be a significant change in memory performance which would show that the short-form video treatment degraded subjects' memory performances. This was at the significance level of 0.05.

3. Results

In this section, we present the results of our experiment and whether there was a significant difference in memory ability between both treatments.

We found that there was a significant difference between memory performance of subjects in both conditions at a p-value of 0.0385, and $p < 0.05$. The t-value was -1.81741. This attests that short-form videos indeed had a negative effect on memory performance.

In the short-form video treatment (V), subjects retained a mean of 6.6 words ($SD = 3.4$), with a median of 6 words, minimum of 3 words, and maximum 14 words. The interquartile range (IQR) was 3.5, indicating moderate variability within the data (Table 1).

Contrastingly, after the relaxation condition (R), subjects retained a mean of 8.45 words ($SD = 2.9$), with a median of 8 words, minimum of 5 words, and maximum of 16 words. Here, we calculated an IQR of 4, which also indicates moderate variability within the data.

Difference score D was calculated by subtracting the words recalled after relaxation from the short-form video word recall performance for every participant. The mean of difference score D was -1.8 ($SD = 2.93$), with a median of -1.5, minimum of -8, maximum of 4, and IQR of 3, indicating moderate variability within the different scores.

Table 1

Overview of words recalled in participants by condition.

Condition	Words Recalled					
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>IQR</i>
Short-form videos (V)	6.6	3.4	6	3	14	3.5
Relaxation (R)	8.45	2.9	8	5	16	4
Difference (D)	-1.8	2.9	-1.5	-8	4	3

Cohen's *d* of 0.59, calculated with the scores from the short-form video condition and relaxation condition, confirmed the significance of the results. This medium effect size indicates that the impact of short-form videos on long-term memory performance is not trivial, and should not be disregarded.

With a one-tailed t-test, we then determined that the difference between treatments was statistically significant, and subjects remembered more by relaxing than by using TikTok ($t = -1.81741$).

3.1 Figures

Figure 2

Distribution of Difference Scores for Word List Recall Memory Tasks.

Note. The distribution of difference scores ($R - V$) in the memory recall test following short-form video and relaxation conditions is displayed. The standard deviations (dashed lines) and mean difference score (blue) are represented by the vertical lines.

4. Discussion

We evaluated the impacts of short-form videos on long-term memory. In this study, subjects were instructed to participate in two sessions testing their long-term memory after watching short-form videos or after relaxing.

First, with our significant p-value, it can be concluded that there was certainly a negative difference between memory performance after using short-form videos and after relaxation. Secondly, we then found that the difference score D showed significant changes. All data suggested that there was interference on memory performance of participants due to using short-form videos.

Therefore, it can be concluded that short-form video platforms such as TikTok, Instagram Reels, YouTube Shorts, and WeChat Channels significantly degrade memory performance. This raises serious concerns, not only for scholars, but for the current and future generations who spend much time on these social media platforms. Additionally, there are alarming implications that come with the conclusion of memory interference in individuals after watching short-form videos; memory interference across a whole generation of young people have yet to be thoroughly studied.

The negative effects of short-form videos on long-term memory are crucial for the growth of a generation. Students who spend much time on social media and their educators, for example, would likely benefit from being informed of short-form videos and their impact on memory retention and learning.

Long-term risks of heavy short-form video consumption could also be studied, given its detrimental impact on long-term memory. Our findings may thus raise implications for limits or regulations on screen time in young adults or users of these platforms overall.

Future studies could examine this effect of memory interference by short-form videos over longer amounts of time, such as over weeks or months. Additionally, it would also be significant if the memory performance of participants within different age groups could be studied.

4.1 Limitations

In this study, there were important limitations and caveats that must be addressed in future studies.

Notable limitations included lack of time to complete the experiment; the full potential of this experiment can be reached in the future if scholars have a full timeline and detailed plan. With more time, scholars can incorporate more subjects and achieve more conclusive results. With more budget, this study could attract more participants, fully including the general population.

Additionally, The sample size of 20 for this study was relatively small and was a significant caveat in the experiment. Future studies are encouraged to include more participants of different backgrounds to produce more comprehensive results.

5. Conclusion

In this experiment, we investigated the impact of short-form videos on long-term memory. We conducted a within-subjects experiment with 20 participants evaluating their memory performance through word-list recall. Memory performance after using short-form video platforms such as TikTok, Instagram Reels, YouTube Shorts, and WeChat Channels were compared to performance after relaxing for 15 minutes. It was found through statistical analyses of the participants' memory performance that there was significant memory interference present in the short-form video condition. This addresses concern for the negative impacts of short-form videos, and raises questions for future studies on the relationship between memory interference and short-form videos.

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